

CURE SIMULATION MODEL FOR RESISTANCE CURED COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY: The resistance heating method for curing thermoset composites has been developed as an alternative to oven, autoclave or hot press curing. The composite interior is heated by passing current through embedded carbon fiber patches. These internal energy sources present a new form of applied thermal loads not found in the traditional cure simulation models, which typically are limited to external boundary conditions. The paper presents a numerical method for predicting temperature, degree of cure, and cure rate for thermoset resin/fiber composites. Finite difference formulas describe the temporal and spatial derivatives of the energy equation. Heat generation terms are linearized over each time interval to ensure compatibility of cure rate and degree of cure with the corresponding temperature. Internal heating, via resistance heating, and external temperature or flux can be applied. Numerical simulations are presented to demonstrate the sensitivity to various input parameters.

KEYWORDS: numerical model, cure simulation, resistance heating, finite difference method

INTRODUCTION

Resin transfer molding and other closed mold thermoset composite manufacturing methods require a cure stage whereby heat is added through devices such as an autoclave, smart press, oven, hot plate or thermal strips. Considerable research has been conducted to develop simulations that describe the temperature profile in composites using boundary conditions appropriate for the particular curing device. For example, a finite element model [1] and implicit finite difference model [2] of an autoclave cure cycle, and a one dimensional ADI (alternating direction implicit) finite difference model for a heated tool plate cure cycle [3] illustrate the use of numerical simulations to predict temperature, degree of cure and rate of cure through the thickness of composites.

Simulations perform another valuable service in that they are used to evaluate the effects of certain processing parameters before manufacturing. For example, a one-dimensional finite difference model was employed to investigate variations in temperature response when fiber and resin properties were altered [4]. The researchers isolated the influence of one resin property without creating a new resin that exactly retained all other properties. Another study simulated the effects of boundary conditions for curing thick composites. Their results suggested thermal spikes can develop at the center of the composite when thick parts are cured with external heat sources [5]. These results were later substantiated with experiments

conducted for closed-mold, thick, fiberglass/epoxy composites cured in an oven [6]. The inability to cure thick parts in an oven initiated the development of a resistance heating method for curing thermoset composites using carbon fiber patches [7].

Unlike the simulations with externally applied heat sources, the resistance heating method requires specification of an interior source of energy. In the resistance heating method the composite is cured by passing current through an embedded carbon fiber patch. Local resistance heating acts as an internal heat source; the resin catalyzes and generates more heat. The combination of the exothermic reaction and thermal conduction drives the cure of the remaining resin. The work presented here describes the numerical model for predicting the temperature and cure profiles when internal resistance heating is applied in a closed mold composite manufacturing method.

NUMERICAL MODEL

Energy Equation

The most general form of the two-dimensional energy equation for the stationary system shown in Figure 1 is

$$\rho C_p \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} - k_x \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial x^2} - k_y \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial y^2} = Q \text{ for } (x, y) \in A_c \quad (1)$$

where ρ is the density, C_p is the specific heat, k_x and k_y are thermal conductivities in the x and y directions, respectively, T is the temperature, and Q represents an internal heat source, such as a chemical reaction. The properties, k_x , k_y , ρ , and C_p , for both the resin and fiber are assumed constant through the cure cycle. The energy evolved during the cure of the resin can be obtained using differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) and is characterized by the heat of reaction of the resin H_r and the degree of cure α ,

$$Q = H_r \frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial t}. \quad (2)$$

Figure 1: Composite cross-section

The DSC output is used to construct an empirical cure kinetic model of Arrhenius-type. For example, the autocatalytic kinetic model for epoxy reactions has the form.

$$\frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial t} = (k_1 + k_2 \alpha^m)(\alpha_f - \alpha)^n \quad (3)$$

where m and n are reaction orders, α_f is the final degree of cure in isothermal DSC scans, and

$$k_i = K_i \exp[-E_i / RT], \quad i = 1, 2, \quad (4)$$

such that K_i is a pre-exponential factor, E_i is the activation energy, and R is the universal gas constant. Table 1 shows cure kinetic values from two separate studies for diglycidyl ether of bishpenol-A (DGEBA) epoxies--both obtained using DSC [8], [9].

The effects of the resistive heating element shown in Figure 1 are included in the model as an internal condition specified at the location of the carbon fiber patch. At the patch, the rate of energy conducted perpendicularly away from the patch is assumed to be balanced by the power, q per unit volume, V_{patch} supplied by an external voltage source.

$$-k_y \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial y^2} = Q_r = \frac{q}{V_{patch}} \quad \text{for } (x, y) \in A_Q. \quad (6)$$

Along with the energy balance in the x-y plane defined by equations (1) and (6), boundary conditions are needed for a complete model description. Although other forms of conditions involving heat transfer coefficients can be specified, this model restricts the application of boundary conditions to temperature and flux:

$$T = T_0, \quad \text{on } S_1 \quad \text{and} \quad \frac{\partial T}{\partial x} = q_0, \quad \text{on } S_2. \quad (7)$$

Table 1. Kinetic Parameters for DGEBA resins.

	EPON 9302 [7]	EPON 826 [8]
K_1 (sec ⁻¹)	25.1×10 ³	144×10 ³
K_2 (sec ⁻¹)	668×10 ⁶	20.8×10 ³
E_1 (kcal/mol)	13.3	15.7
E_2 (kcal/mol)	17.8	10.3
m	1.6	1.68 - 2.042×10 ⁻³ T(°K)
n	1.4	0.32 + 2.042×10 ⁻³ T(°K)
α_f	- 0.437 + 2.39×10 ⁻³ T(°K)	1

The complete boundary value problem, equations (1) and (6) with boundary conditions (7) are approximated using finite differences in conjunction with a linearization scheme over the time interval.

Linearization Model

The finite difference formulas for the spatial and temporal derivatives on the left-hand side of (1) and (6) are given as a first order backward difference and second order central differences,

$$\frac{\partial T}{\partial t} = \frac{T(t) - T(t - \Delta t)}{\Delta t} \quad (8)$$

$$\frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial x^2} = \frac{T(x - \Delta h_x) - 2T(x) + T(x + \Delta h_x)}{\Delta h_x^2} \quad (9)$$

$$\frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial y^2} = \frac{T(y - \Delta h_y) - 2T(y) + T(y + \Delta h_y)}{\Delta h_y^2} \quad (10)$$

where Δt , Δh_x , Δh_y are the time and space intervals. Using these difference formulas throughout region $A_C + A_Q$ yields the generalized form

$$[K] \{T\}^i = f_1 \{T\}^{i-1} + f_2 \{Q\}^i + f_2 \{Q_r\} \quad (11)$$

where $[K]$ includes the coefficient matrix for temperatures, f_1 and f_2 are constants based on resin and fiber material properties, and the superscript i represents the current (i th) time step. $\{Q_r\}$ does not vary with time; therefore, no superscript is shown. Notice that $\{Q\}$, the energy evolved from the chemical reaction, is evaluated in the current time step. The term is linearized based on the previous rate of cure and the rate of cure with respect to the temperature.

$$\{Q\}^i = H_r \left\{ \frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial t} \right\}^i = H_r \left\{ \frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial t} \right\}^{i-1} + H_r \frac{d}{dT} \frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial t} \Big|_{-i-1} (\{T\}^i - \{T\}^{i-1}). \quad (12)$$

Even though equation (11) can be expressed in terms that are dependent on times, i and $i-1$, further linearization over the interval is recommended, particularly since the load or source vector contains terms that vary exponentially [9].

Consider a simplified form of (11) at an arbitrary generalized time step, θ

$$[K]^\theta \{T\}^\theta = \{F\}^\theta \quad (13)$$

where θ is a dimensionless quantity that ranges from 0 to 1 such that

$$\theta = \frac{t - t^n}{t^{n+1} - t^n} = \frac{t - t^n}{\Delta t}. \quad (14)$$

The assumption that the resin and fiber properties, (conductivity, heat capacity and density) do not vary with time means the linearization scheme need only be applied to $\{T\}$ and $\{F\}$.

$$\{T\}^\theta = (1 - \theta)\{T\}^{i-1} + \theta\{T\}^i \quad (15)$$

$$\{F\}^{\theta} = (1-\theta)\{F\}^{i-1} + \theta\{F\}^i \quad (16)$$

At the limits $\theta=0$ or $\theta=1$, the form is identically a forward or backward difference, respectively. Since the backward difference formulation is unconditionally stable, all results presented here will be obtained with $\theta=1$. Once the linearizations are applied, the final form of the model is

$$[K_r]^i \{T\}^i = F_2 \{T\}^{i-2} + F_1 \{T\}^{i-1} + f_2 H_r \left\{ \frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial t} \right\}^{i-1} + f_2 \{Q_R\} \quad (17)$$

where

$$[K_r] = \theta[K]^i - f_2 H_r \frac{d}{dT} \frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial t} \Big|_{-i-1} [I] \quad (18)$$

$$F_2 = (1-\theta)f_1 \quad (19)$$

$$F_1 = (1-\theta)[K] + \theta f_1 [I] - f_2 H_r \frac{d}{dT} \frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial t} \Big|_{-i-1} [I]. \quad (20)$$

NUMERICAL SIMULATIONS

The numerical model was checked for convergence for element size and time interval. The model is more sensitive to the time step. This is primarily a result of the cure kinetic model containing exponential terms. An adaptive time step would be desirable; however, for the work presented here a constant time step was chosen for the entire cure cycle. For consistency in reporting and comparing a variety of temperature versus time and degree-of-cure versus time results, the same time step was used for all simulations regardless of whether that particular level of refined time step was needed.

Figure 2: Schematic of cross-section for numerical simulations.

Parametric Study

A series of numerical simulations was conducted to evaluate a variety of parameters-either material properties, mold thickness or boundary conditions. The results presented focus on the latter two since they pertain to internal resistance heating in combination with, or compared to, external heating sources such as a hot press or hot plate. The model will have the geometry as shown in Figure 2 and will use the resin model for Shell EPON 826.

Figures 3, 4 and 5 illustrate the effects of varying the boundary conditions: heat source and magnitude of thermal loads. For example, consider the arrangement shown in Figure 2 with $q=0$, i.e., no carbon patches. Heat is applied in the form of an external source applied at the top and bottom of the composite. When that source input varies, even slightly, i.e., by 5°C , the exothermic reaction can cause a significant change in the temperature profile at the center of the composite. Seventy-five percent of the cure occurs at the peak of the exothermic reaction when $T_0=40^{\circ}\text{C}$, whereas only 60% of the cure occurs at the peak of the reaction for $T_0=35^{\circ}\text{C}$. This same effect of thermal spiking was observed in experimental work with 50 mm thick fiberglass/epoxy (20% fiber volume fraction) when cured in an oven [7] and also by simulation of thick carbon/epoxy laminates cured under pressure and temperature [5].

Figure 3: Temperature and Degree of Cure versus Time for $T_0=40^{\circ}\text{C}$, 35°C , with $q=0$, $H=25.4$ mm.

Figure 4: Temperature and Degree of Cure versus Time for conduction only, external heat source only, and resistive heating with external heat source. $H=25.4$ mm. $T_0=35^{\circ}\text{C}$

The use of resistant heating in conjunction with external heating sources can reduce the effect of thermal spiking as shown in Figure 4. The curve marked conduction is a temperature plot at the center of the specimen if the heating is due only to conduction, i.e., no chemical reaction or internal heating. The other curves represent the temperature and degree of cure when the same external heat source is applied but in one case the resistant heating patches are activated by a power source. The degree of cure at the peak exotherm is approximately 10% lower (0.67 degree of cure versus 0.60 degree of cure) when the combined method of heating is employed. This is due in part to the initial heating at the center of the composite due to the heating patch. The exothermic peak temperature is also lowered when including the additional power source. This may be due to initiating cure earlier with a more gradual release of the exothermic energy. Even though the steady state temperature is slightly increased due to the additional heat source, the cure cycle profile has been improved--a lower peak temperature is reached in less time.

At this point, one may think that by increasing the power to the patch, the maximum temperature will continue to decrease and the time to peak will be reduced. In fact, as shown in Figure 5, this is not the case. For a given external source, a small amount of internal power can decrease the time to reach peak temperature and lower the peak temperature; however, additional internal heating will cause the peak temperature to increase, and the time to reach peak temperature to decrease. The amount of cure at peak temperature is not significantly affected. An optimum combination of external and internal heating could produce the desired rate of cure and length of cure cycle. Other options involve the use of feedback whereby the manufacturers recommended cure cycle is controlled by cycling the power to the patch as needed [11].

Figure 5: Temperature and Degree of Cure versus Time for resistant heating power ($q=2$ cal/s, 1 cal/s) supplied to the heating patches. $H=25.4$ mm. $T_0=35^\circ\text{C}$

Finally, the effect of internal heating was investigated for composites of varying thickness. Figure 6 shows that as the part becomes thinner, the application of resistance heating becomes less significant. Thick parts regardless of how they are cured are subjected to the same difficulty--an exponential increase in peak temperature as the thickness increases linearly; however no appreciable increase in the degree of cure at peak temperature occurs.

Figure 6: Temperature and Degree of Cure versus Time for $H=12.7$ mm, 19.1 mm and 25.4 mm with $q=1$ cal/s, $T_0=35^\circ\text{C}$

CONCLUSIONS

The resistance heating method of cure can be modeled using a two-dimensional finite difference scheme with an internal source term that is directly related to the power per unit volume supplied by the external electric circuit. Simulations conducted to study the influence of a variety of processing parameters indicated that a combination of external heating and internal heating can reduce thermal spiking in thick parts. Furthermore a gradual increase in temperature at the center of composites is recognized as a means of minimizing thermal spiking and thereby reducing the degree of cure achieved at the peak temperature.

As composites manufacturing moves further into markets that require mass production of thick section parts, or parts with large geometries that do not lend themselves to oven, hot press or autoclave curing, resistance heating may become more prevalent. The current simulation model addresses the need to simulate processing conditions and investigate placement of internal heating elements. To date, the model is restricted to two internal resistance heating elements; however, work is ongoing to develop more flexibility in the input parameters and boundary specification.

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